

**CONTEXTUALIZED ASSESSMENT TOOL FOR GRADE 9 STUDENTS IN
CHOOSING THE TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION
(TLE) SPECIALIZATION COURSES: INPUTS FOR A
PROPOSED INTERVENTION PROGRAM**

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Contextualized Assessment Tool for Grade 9 Students in Choosing the Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Specialization Courses: Inputs for a Proposed Intervention Program

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Abstract

This research study aimed to seek answers through contextualized assessment tools for grade 9 students at Rizal High School during the school year 2023-2024. This study was undertaken during the fourth grading period of the school year 2022-2023 of batch A respondents and the first grading period of the school year 2023-2024 of batch B respondents. The assessment tool that was developed relative to the perceived needs of the grade 9 student respondents was 42-item contextualized questionnaire based on John Holland's Career Choice Theory (RIASEC). The evaluation of the experts on the contextualized assessment tool got a total grand mean of 3.78 which is interpreted as strongly agree in the following indicators: content, relevance, clarity and coherence. In addition, the prevailing trait of grade 9 student respondents in Batch A and B is on social aspect that accounts for 27.78% of the respondents and the lowest trait that reflects on the conducted survey is on enterprising that accounts for 5.83% of the student respondents. The prevailing TLE specialization based on the result of the contextualized questionnaire of grade 9 student respondents is cookery which has 46.67% for Batch A and B. Next to it is on dressmaking which got the percentage of 14.86%. On the other hand, the least TLE specialization fell on Electrical Installation and Maintenance (EIM) with 3.47% as least interesting TLE specialization to take. With a p-value of 0.00 and at the significance level of 0.05, the social trait, as the highest overall RIASEC trait result had an effect on the grade nine respondents' choice of TLE specialization after the administration of the contextualized assessment tool. Also, with a p-value of 0.00, at the significance level of 0.05, the relationship between the sex of student-respondents and the TLE specialization result of the contextualized assessment tool is statistically significant.

Keywords: *TLE, intervention program, contextualized assessment*

Introduction

Teachers are considered helping hands in achieving such rights and advocate for students to choose the best path for them. Choosing a career is one of many crucial decisions the students make, in deciding on a course of action. This decision has an impact on them for the rest of their lives. Teachers play a pivotal role in assisting and helping students choose the best academic path for them. They have the expertise, wisdom, and comprehension needed to guide students through the vast array of possibilities open to them as mentors and instructors.

In comparison to young adults, secondary school students frequently worry about what they will do with their lives (Brennan, 2021). The days pass quickly when regular employment availability cannot cater to the large number of young people who finish their secondary education. These young people are anxious about the early employment they'll be facing in society and looking for efficient jobs, fulfilling jobs both inside and outside of those societies (Brende, 2020). The study's intended respondents are Grade 9 students aged 14 to 20. As stated in the journal article of Malabanan (2019) the abovementioned ages are under the adolescence stage, where these young people seek their independence and build their self-confidence throughout this phase. This includes their awareness of their interests and hobbies, which helps in choosing the appropriate path to take in school specialization subjects.

Department of Education curriculum in grade nine students includes the offering of Technology and livelihood education (TLE) along with its specialization courses (Department of Education, 2022). Students in high school learn the technical concepts they would encounter in daily life through the Technology and Livelihood Education course (TLE). The law known as RA 10647, which enhances the ladder connection between technical vocational education and higher education training, serves as the legislative foundation for TLE instruction (Philippine Official Gazette, 2022).

Rizal High School, usually referred to as RHS is a secondary educational establishment based in Pasig, Metro Manila, Philippines (Rizal High School, 2022). From 1993 to 2005, it had the title of the largest secondary school in the world (Guinness World Records, 2022). The school cultivates well-rounded enrollees and holds its students accountable for their academic progress.

It is within this context that the researcher is motivated to this study and develop a tool to enhance schools' capacity to support Rizal High School Grade 9 students in making informed decisions about their career ambitions and potentially enhance educational and economic attainment by promoting a more contextualized understanding of career choice.

The study aims to uplift the education that can be offered not only with the class that the researcher handles but also with the curriculum that the school offers, Rizal High School, and with the other institutions that can be influenced by this study. This study is a monomer for amelioration where inputs for an intervention program can be drafted. This paper serves as a fundamental resource to display the passion of educators in honing the future of their students directed by their employment and other aspirations in the students' lives.

Research Questions

This research aimed to seek answers through contextualized assessment tools for grade 9 students at Rizal High School during the school year 2022-2023 and school year 2023-2024. This study was conducted with the following research questions:

1. What assessment tool was developed based on the modification of John Holland's Career Choice Theory using Polat, Bajak, and Zhumaeva approach for paraphrasing and rewording a challenging text?
2. What was the evaluation of the experts on the contextualized assessment in terms of the following variables?
 - 2.1. content;
 - 2.2. relevance;
 - 2.3. clarity; and
 - 2.4. coherence?
3. What was the result of the administered assessment tool of the students' respondents in terms of the following:
 - 3.1. Realistic (R);
 - 3.2. Investigative (I);
 - 3.3. Artistic (A);
 - 3.4. Social (S);
 - 3.5. Enterprising (E); and
 - 3.6. Conventional (C)?
4. What were the TLE specialization distributions of the student respondents after the administration of the contextualized assessment tool?
5. Was there a significant relationship between TLE specialization results based on the contextualized assessment tool administered to student respondents and the RIASEC trait result?
6. Was there a significant difference between TLE specialization results based on the contextualized assessment tool administered to student respondents and the actual TLE specializations taken by the students?
7. Was there a significant relationship between TLE specialization results based on the contextualized assessment tool administered to respondents when grouped according to profile:
 - 7.1. age;
 - 7.2. sex; and
 - 7.3. family income?
8. What intervention program was proposed based on the result of the study?

Literature Review

Choosing a career is typically an exciting and terrifying affair. A person might feel the tug in different directions if they have diverse strengths. By selecting a job route, that person can gain a deeper understanding of their personality, hobbies, beliefs, preferred way of life, and financial demands. Even if it might be influenced by family members, professors, coaches, and friends, it is better when it is in line with the person's talents, interests, and skill sets (Brubaker, 2022).

Students in high school learn the technical concepts they would encounter in daily life through the Technology and Livelihood Education course (TLE). The legislative foundation for TLE instruction is provided by RA 10647, a statute that strengthens the ladderized relationship between technical vocational education and higher education training. A variety of aspects, including real-world work, hazy difficulties, various sources, teamwork, reflection, a multidisciplinary approach, integrated assessment, polished products, and various interpretations and outcomes are taken into account when teaching TLE (Basal, 2019).

According to John Holland's Theory of Career Choice (RIASEC), which was published by Armstrong (2020), people favor working in environments where they may engage with others who share their interests. They look for situations where they may apply their knowledge and abilities, demonstrate their attitudes and values, and engage in enjoyable tasks and challenges. The interaction of personality and environment influences behavior. In line with this, another article published by Shears (2019) stated that Holland has investigated the factors that influence occupational choices. Family, close friends, teachers, and other adult role models, as well as experiences from school, the workplace, and leisure activities, must all have a significant influence. Holland's theory, an interactional model, is based on a typology of people and their circumstances.

Numerous vocational aptitude tests, including our free test, are based on the John Holland-developed RIASEC paradigm. The acronym RIASEC stands for realistic, investigative, artistic, social, entrepreneurial, and conventional, and it relates to six major personality traits. Holland claims that the RIASEC hypothesis may be used to categorize every individual and every profession. For instance, if the social score is high, it is advised that the work in the medical or educational sectors. But most people only pick two or three personality qualities. Additionally, the majority of professions perform well on two or three traits (Malabanan, 2019).

An educator must draft a comprehensive assessment system that is relevant to the students. According to Kosimov (2022), assessments should be created and used by TLE teachers for the needs of the students. Assessment is crucial to raising the caliber of the curriculum.

The area of education is faced with both daunting challenges and whole new responsibilities as a result of the swift and complicated changes in today's society. The curriculum needs to be revised to keep up with these developments and the cultural change that is occurring at an accelerated rate. The trend is always changing, and as a result, the curriculum, the cornerstone of any learning institution, has developed into a dynamic process. The increasing emphasis on fundamental skills is one particular response to the demand for such change. Future educational developments will place more emphasis on applying knowledge than simply collecting it. To give students the freedom to select and use their information, a curriculum's emphasis must go beyond traditional methods (Canzana, 2019).

Students are affected by the assessment methods used by their teachers. In addition to analyzing the outcomes of standardized tests, educators also create their examinations in a variety of forms, assign homework, mark the projects that their students create or acquire from textbooks or reference materials, and construct their evaluations. They ask questions and solicit answers from individuals or groups of students. They also listen, observe, and interview students. When teachers share their findings and evaluations with students, the learning process is influenced in some way (Basal, 2019).

Methodology

Research Design

Mixed method was the research approach whereby researcher collected and analyze both quantitative and qualitative based on literature within the same study. In order to have a thorough grasp of the current research, a mixed method approach in research was utilized by the researcher that integrates both quantitative and qualitative procedures within this study. Using both quantitative and qualitative data collecting and analysis methods to the advantage, this strategy enables the researcher to draft a more comprehensive picture of the phenomenon that the researcher studied.

Participants

The data of this study were derived from two different school years of grade nine students studying at Rizal High School. The current study utilized a sampling technique named simple random sampling. A subset of a statistical population called a simple random sample is one in which each member has an equal chance of being chosen. Simple random sampling is a completely random technique for choosing the sample.

Instrument

The researcher employed the contextualized assessment tool that was developed utilizing both John Holland's Self-directed Search and the RIASEC personality theory (SDS). Self-directed search (SDS) was created by American psychologist John Holland's theory, which divides people and work environments into six categories. Some of the subcategories are realistic, investigative, creative, social, entrepreneurial, and traditional.

Procedure

The researcher secured letters of approval to conduct the study to the school principal of Rizal High School and to the division superintendent of the City of Pasig. The researcher secured the total population of grade nine student-respondents of both batch A and batch B, in the fourth grading of the school year 2022-2023 and the first quarter of the school year 2023-2024. The researcher drafted the contextualized test based on John Holland's Career Choice Theory also known as the RIASEC theory of personality. This was validated by the experts.

The statistician then processed the scores given by each expert to test the internal validity or Cronbach's alpha. The statistician utilized the SPSS software to estimate the validity of the aforesaid contextualized test. Along with the scoring of the validators was the pilot testing done on grade nine students who were not part of the sample population that was tested for the overall analysis of results presented in this study. These students who participated in the pilot study submitted their responses to test the internal validity and integrity of the questionnaire utilizing Cronbach's Alpha by the statistician of this paper.

Once the test mentioned above was approved, the researcher proceeded to the data gathering. The researcher utilized simple random sampling to ensure the variability and representation of the population were accurate. After the 720 samples were determined, the parental consent was distributed and explained to the participants. A minor assent was secured by each student-respondent. This is used in relation to studies involving minors or those who are not old enough to give their own free and informed permission. In this situation, the researcher asked the minor student-respondents for their consent in addition to getting it from their parents or legal guardians. Before disseminating the survey form, the researcher gave the participants seven days to return the parental consent form. The form consists of minor assent and the contextualized test. The researcher enforced a verbal explanation along with the written informed consent attached to the survey form. The researcher then disseminated the survey form that allowed the participants to answer the assessment tool. The researcher explained the meaning of whatever the highest characteristic they get from the assessment tool.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical consideration has been given importance by the researcher since the participants are considered minors and the Philippines is still recovering from the COVID-19 pandemic. The researcher secured minor assent from the participants and documentation of their

parent’s permission for them to take part in the study. The consent entails complete information about the study and how their child is part of the current study. On the other hand, the researcher included the minor assent on the first page of the survey form entailing the details about the study and should there be any risk on them. In the quantitative phase, the researcher visited the rooms of the respondents to explain to every class about the researcher’s study and complete details about it. Then, the researcher disseminated the survey form which the respondents answered. The researcher ensured the anonymity and confidentiality of the information they shared in the aforesaid form.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Developed Assessment Tool based on John Holland’s Career Choice Theory

Table 1. *Developed Assessment Tool based on John Holland’s Career Choice Theory*

<i>John Holland’s Career Choice Theory</i>	<i>Modification</i>	<i>Theory Used</i>
John Holland’s Career Choice theory finds its practical application in evaluating individuals based on their prominent personality types and aligning them with the environmental facets or potential careers. According to the theory, the greater the alignment between an individual traits and the requirements of a job, the more favorable the prospects for positive career outcomes such as satisfaction, perseverance, and success.	The current research employed a contextualized assessment tool to match student-respondents with the TLE specialization offered at their current school, Rizal High School, as outlined in John Holland’s Choice Theory.	Polat, Y., Bajak, S., & Zhumaeva, A. (2021). A New Approach for Paraphrasing and Rewording a challenging Text. Arab World English Journal, 158-168.
<p>Outlined below are original statements on the assessment of RIASEC (Realistic, Investigative, Artistic, Social, Enterprising, and Conventional) traits of an individual, that was modified in this study.</p> <p>I like to work on cars I am an ambitious person, I set goals for myself. I am a creative person I like selling things I like to build things I pay attention to details I would like to start my own business. I like putting things together or assemble together or assembling things</p>	<p>Outlined below are modified statements on the contextualized assessment assess not only the RIASEC trait of the respondents but all so the TLE specialization that matches their interest based on their scoring to the mentioned questionnaire.</p> <p>I am having fun on exploring refrigerators and air-conditioning tool I dream of having my own boutique/ clothing line I am having fun drawing various building/houses I dream of selling my drawings or house designs to make a profit out of it I like to build things and do wirings that I do with repairing things/installing simple machines I dream about putting up my own computer shop I like to explore system units or hardware of computers</p>	

Table 1 entails the statements published in John Holland’s Career Choice Theory that were modified by the researcher in this paper. The first statement is, I like to work on cars, this is a statement under investigative trait, in which it is modified into, I am having fun on exploring refrigerators and air-conditioning tools. The latter statement pertains to an investigative person and relates to an Electrical Installation and Maintenance (EIM) TLE specialization as supported by the theory of Polat, Bajak, and Zhumaeva (2021), in which these researchers cited about surface and deep structures in paraphrasing or modifying an assessment tool. The underlying essence of a sentence is captured by the deep structure, while the surface structure is the visible form of that sentence. By examining the surface structure, a language can be returned to its original state, akin to resetting it to its default settings, preparing it for modification. The second and third statements that were modified are, I am an ambitious person, I set goals for myself, and I am a creative person, these were written into, I dream of having my own boutique/ clothing line, and I am having fun drawing various buildings/houses, respectively. These were modified based on the aforesaid topic of surface and deep structure.

The fourth, fifth, and sixth statements were, I like selling things, I like to build things, and I pay attention to details, these were modified into, I dream of selling my drawings or house designs to make a profit out of it, I like to build things and do wirings of things, I am particular to details of the wirings that I do with repairing things/ installing simple machines. The original statements mentioned from John Holland’s Career Choice Theory were general statements of traits that were put into specific situations relatable to student-respondents of this study. The modification was supported by the topic about kernels and propositions of the researchers Polat, Bajak, and Zhumaeva (2021), that detailed statements are often more engaging and interesting to the audience. By including specific examples, anecdotes, or descriptive language, the statement becomes more vivid and compelling, capturing the reader’s or listener’s attention and sustaining their interest.

The seventh and eighth statements were, I would like to start my own business, and I like putting things together or assembling things, these were modified into, I dream about putting up my own computer shop, and I like to explore system units or hardware of computers. The original statements mentioned from John Holland’s Career Choice Theory were restated in the assessment tool utilized in the current study related to the specific interests, and relatable situations by student-respondents of this study.

Evaluation of Experts on the Contextualized Assessment Tool in Terms of Content, Relevance, Clarity and Coherence

Table 2. *Evaluation of the Experts on the Contextualized Assessment in terms of Content*

Indicators	\bar{x}	VI
1. The items in the instrument are neither too narrow nor limited in their content	4.00	SA
2. The items in the instrument provide depth of content for the targeted respondents	3.80	SA
3. The items of the instrument show a balance of content with the objectives it is directed at.	3.60	SA
4. The instrument possesses content adequate to cover its purpose.	3.80	SA
5. The instrument reflects well-written instructions for the respondents.	3.60	SA
Overall Mean	3.76	SA

Legend: VI- Verbal Interpretation, \bar{x} - mean, 3.25-4.00 (SA-Strongly Agree), 2.50-3.24 (A-Agree), 1.75-2.49 (D- Disagree), 1.00-1.74 (SD- Strongly Disagree).

The mentioned tool has an overall mean of 3.76 with verbal interpretation of strongly agree, in delivering the content of the questionnaire. The table collectively indicates that the instrument's comprehensive and well-rounded content is suited to its target audience and goals. Frey (2022) supports the mentioned analysis where he stated that well-written and unambiguous instructions for the respondents cover the good content of a research instrument.

Table 3. *Evaluation of the Experts on the Contextualized Assessment in Terms of Relevance*

Indicators	\bar{x}	VI
1. The items in the instrument are essential or important to be included in the instrument	4.00	SA
2. The items in the instrument are relevant to the coverage of important data appropriate to the situation or respondents	3.80	SA
3. The statements in the instrument are relatable such that the respondents will be able to answer the instrument accurately	4.00	SA
4. The instrument reflects the experiences of the target population and elicits interest in accomplishing the survey completely	4.00	SA
5. The instrument is considered up-to-date with the current trends in society.	3.40	A
Overall Mean	3.84	SA

The highest mean score is 4.00 with the verbal interpretation of strongly agree, on the statements that the items in the instrument are essential or important to be included in the instrument, the statements in the instrument are relatable such that the respondents will be able to answer the instrument accurately and the instrument reflects the experiences of the target population and elicits interest in accomplishing the survey completely.

Martin (2019) stated in his article that an assessment tool that encapsulates good relevance means that the questionnaire's content closely adheres to the study's goals and successfully gathers the pertinent data required to answer the questions or hypotheses.

Table 4. *Evaluation of the Experts on the Contextualized Assessment in terms of Clarity*

Indicators	\bar{x}	VI
1. The instrument is clear with appropriate semantics and syntax	3.80	SA
2. The terms used in the instrument are easy to comprehend	3.70	SA
3. The statements in the instrument did not elicit ambiguity	3.60	SA
4. The instrument displays a clear description of the situation that needs to be answered by the respondents	3.70	SA
5. The overall format of the instrument is clear	3.70	SA
Overall Mean	3.70	SA

The evaluators' overall mean score about clarity is 3.70 with the verbal interpretation of strongly agree. A study by Gael and Cohn (2022) entails that, when evaluating an assessment tool's clarity, it's essential to take its claims' clearness into account. Clarity is the achievability and practicality of putting the words in the assessment tool into action.

The evaluators' overall mean score about clarity is 3.80 with the verbal interpretation of strongly agree. The assessment tool drafted by the researcher has a logical connection and consistency between ideas. Brookhart (2019) stated that a coherent assessment instrument establishes clear connections between the research objectives and the questions or tasks presented to participants.

Table 5. Evaluation of the Experts on the Contextualized Assessment in terms of Coherence

Indicators	\bar{x}	VI
1. The instrument has an appropriate sample of items for the construct being measured	3.80	SA
2. The statements in the instrument are directed to its purpose in determining the interest of the target population	3.80	SA
3. The statements in the instrument are consistent with its whole construct	3.80	SA
4. The whole instrument is logically directed to its purpose	4.00	SA
5. The instrument reflects coherence in the overall setup	3.60	SA
Overall Mean	3.80	SA

The Result of the Administered Assessment Tool of the Students’ Respondents based on RIASEC Traits

Table 6. The Result of the Administered Assessment Tool of the Students’ Respondents in terms of RIASEC Traits

Trait	Batch A (school year 2022-2023)		Batch B (school year 2023-2024)		Overall	
	F	%	f	%	f	%
a. Realistic	29	8.05	29	8.50	58	8.06
b. Investigative	95	26.39	88	24.44	183	25.42
c. Artistic	39	10.83	36	10.00	75	10.42
d. Social	104	28.89	96	26.67	200	27.78
e. Enterprising	20	5.56	22	6.11	42	5.83
f. Conventional	73	20.28	89	24.72	162	22.50
Total respondents	360	100	360	100	720	100

The students who are part of the 28% that answered social take pleasure in facilitating the growth, learning, and participation of others in group activities. The mentioned analysis is strengthened by the penned article on the website of Terence (2021) which published that individuals who are social in trait usually enjoy social interaction, are good under pressure, and are concerned about how people get along with each other.

On the other hand, 6% of the sample respondents are Enterprising in trait. Armstrong (2020) published in his journal article that enterprising individuals take chances and are born leaders. These enterprising individuals are people who will enjoy business once they graduate, have greater financial aspirations, are prepared to take calculated risks, and are confident in their public personas.

TLE Specialization Distribution of the Student Respondents After the Administration of the Contextualized Assessment Tool

Table 7. TLE Specialization Distribution of the Student Respondents after the Administration of the Contextualized Assessment Tool

TLE Specialization	Batch A (school year 2022-2023)		Batch B (school year 2023-2024)		Overall	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
	a. ICT (Information and Communication Technologies)	31	8.60	46	12.78	77
b. Beauty care	50	13.89	54	15.00	104	14.44
c. Drafting	38	10.56	33	9.17	71	9.86
d. Dressmaking	64	17.8	43	11.94	107	14.86
e. Cookery	171	47.5	165	45.83	336	46.67
f. EIM (Electrical Installation and Maintenance)	6	1.67	19	5.28	25	3.47
Total respondents	360	100	360	100	720	100

There are 47% based on the contextualized assessment tool that leans toward Cookery as TLE specialization befits their interest.

In the Cookery TLE class, students not only acquired cooking techniques for chicken, meat, and fish but also gained valuable knowledge and skills that can significantly improve their lives and yield positive outcomes.

Jumamil and Pelayo (2023) stated that an essential component of independence and self-sufficiency is part of learning in cookery class. The two mentioned researchers also published that those who are knowledgeable about nutrition, food safety, and culinary methods

are better able to prepare their meals and choose healthier foods.

Test of Significant Association of TLE Specialization Results based on the Contextualized Assessment Tool Administered to Student Respondents and the RIASEC Trait Result

Table 8. *Test of Significant Association Between TLE Specialization Results based on the Contextualized Assessment Tool Administered to Student Respondents and the RIASEC Trait Result: Batch A*

Respondent		Value	df	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Batch A	x2	146.430	25	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
(Grade nine respondents school year 2022-2023) (n=360)	Likelihood Ratio	119.011	25	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant

It can be concluded that the student respondents and TLE specialization as a result of the contextualized assessment tool is statistically significant. The social trait, as the highest RIASEC trait result in Batch B had an effect on their choice of TLE specialization after the administration of the mentioned questionnaire.

The analysis mentioned is strengthened by the article of Terence (2021) which he stated that social individuals perform well under pressure, due to their sociable nature. The respondents of the current study appreciate the time constraints imposed by their teachers when completing dishes during the cookery class.

Table 9. *Test of Significant Association Between TLE Specialization Results based on the Contextualized Assessment Tool Administered to Student Respondents and the RIASEC Trait Result: Batch B*

Respondent		Value	df	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Batch B	x2	134.485	25	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
(Grade nine respondents school year 2023-2024) (n=360)	Likelihood Ratio	135.353	25	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant

It can be inferred that most of the student respondents are social students who look for opportunities to collaborate, as they develop dishes that match the nutritional value of the people they are serving during cookery class. This affirms to the statement of Terence (2021) published in his study that social individuals tend to favor engaging in conversations to resolve issues and utilize interpersonal skills, attributes that Batch B respondents can apply when confronting challenges in the cookery class environment.

Table 10. *Test of Significant Difference Between TLE Specialization Results based on the Contextualized Assessment Tool Administered to Student Respondents and the RIASEC Trait Result: Overall*

Respondent		Value	Df	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Overall	x2	258.676	25	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
(All grade nine respondents) (n=720)	Likelihood Ratio	232.497	25	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant

It can be concluded that the association between the overall RIASEC trait result and the TLE specialization result of the assessment tool is statistically significant. This implies that, the social trait, as the overall RIASEC trait result had an effect on their choice of TLE specialization after the administration of the mentioned questionnaire.

Test of Significant Difference Between TLE Specialization Results based on the Contextualized Assessment Tool Administered to Student Respondents and the Actual TLE Specializations taken by the Students, Batch A and B

Table 11. *Significant Difference Between TLE Specialization Results based on the Contextualized Assessment Tool Administered and the Actual TLE Specializations taken by the Students: Batch A*

Distinct Values	Off-Diagonal Cases	Observed MH Statistic	Mean MH Statistic	Std. MH Statistic	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
6	306	1061.000	1127.000	-3.067	0.002	Reject H ₀	Significant

The result implies that the association between the Batch A respondents' actual TLE specialization and the TLE specialization result of the contextualized assessment tool is statistically significant. Hence, there is a notable contrast between the TLE specialization of Batch A students in their ninth-grade year during the 2022-2023 academic year and the outcomes of the contextualized questionnaire they underwent. As the questionnaire completed by the participants includes statements reflecting their interests, it indicates that the desired TLE specialization of the respondents does not align with their actual TLE specialization.

The result in table 12 implies that the difference between the Batch B respondents' actual TLE specialization and the TLE specialization result of the contextualized assessment tool is statistically significant. Hence, there is a notable contrast between the TLE specialization of Batch B students in their ninth-grade year during the 2022-2023 academic year and the outcomes of the contextualized questionnaire

they underwent.

Table 12. Significant Difference Between TLE Specialization Results based on the Contextualized Assessment Tool Administered and the Actual TLE Specializations taken by the students: Batch B

Distinct Values	Off-Diagonal Cases	Observed MH Statistic	Mean MH Statistic	Std. MH Statistic	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
6	303	1078.000	1129.500	-2.370	0.018	Reject H ₀	Significant

The result implies that the difference between the overall respondents' actual TLE specialization and the TLE specialization result of the contextualized assessment tool is statistically significant. Hence, there is a notable contrast between the overall TLE specialization of student respondents in their ninth-grade year and the outcomes of the contextualized questionnaire they underwent. The questionnaire, which reflects their interests, suggests that the preferred TLE specialization of the participants does not match their actual TLE focus.

Table 13. Significant Difference Between TLE Specialization Results based on the Contextualized Assessment Tool Administered and the Actual TLE Specializations taken by the Students: Overall

Distinct Values	Off-Diagonal Cases	Observed MH Statistic	Mean MH Statistic	Std. MH Statistic	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
6	609	2139.000	2256.500	-3.842	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant

Test of Significance Relationship Between TLE Specialization Results based on the Contextualized Assessment Tool Administered to Respondents when Grouped according to Profile such as Age, Sex, Family Income

Table 14. Significant Relationship Between TLE Specialization Results based on the Contextualized Assessment Tool administered to Respondents when grouped according to Age

Respondent	Value	df	p-value
Overall (n=720)	x ²	35	0.432
Likelihood Ratio	35.626	35	0.439

It can be concluded that the association between the age of student respondents and the TLE specialization result of the contextualized assessment tool is statistically insignificant. Therefore, the ages of the respondents ranging from 14 years old to 20 years old do not have an effect on their choice of TLE specialization after the administration of the mentioned questionnaire.

Table 15. Significant Relationship Between TLE Specialization Results based on the Contextualized Assessment Tool administered to Respondents when grouped according to Sex

Respondent	Value	Df	P-Value
Overall (N=720)	X ²	10	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	92.531	10	0.000

It can be concluded that the association between the sex of student respondents and the TLE specialization result of the contextualized assessment tool is statistically significant. Therefore, the sex of the respondents where females are notable participants, had an effect on their choice of TLE specialization after the administration of the mentioned questionnaire.

Table 16. Significant Relationship Between TLE Specialization Results based on the Contextualized Assessment Tool administered to Respondents when grouped according to Family Income

Respondent	Value	df	p-value
Overall (n=720)	x ²	265	0.507
Likelihood Ratio	211.775	265	0.993

It can be concluded that the association between the family income of student respondents and the TLE specialization result of the contextualized assessment tool is statistically insignificant.

Therefore, the family income of the respondents does not affect the TLE specialization after the administration of the mentioned questionnaire.

Proposed Intervention Program, based on the Result of the Current Study

Title: Utilization of the Contextualized Assessment Tool Aligning Students' Interests and TLE Specialization Offered at Rizal High

School

Rationale

The contextualized assessment tool drafted by the researcher enables students to gain valuable insights into their traits, skills, interests, and TLE specialization preferences. Respondents are better able to grasp their strengths and match them with the demands of TLE specialization educational pathways. This empowers the respondents to make choices about the most suitable TLE specialization that resonates with their unique attributes. TLE specializations are offered during the grade nine school year of students in Junior High School. Various aspects were taken into consideration by the school administration in the provision of slot vacancies for the students to take certain TLE specializations. There are instances that more classes are required for a specific subject area due to the demand of students who choose to take such specialization. However, favors are not given to all the students who prefer to be enrolled in their chosen TLE specialization due to limited resources and the number of teachers who can accommodate such classes. This event specifically occurs at Rizal High School, Division of Pasig City.

Hence, in the currently concluded study, it was found that the contextualized assessment tool drafted by the researcher covered enough items that give accuracy to the assessment of students and help them be enlightened to their strengths that can be utilized once they immerse themselves in TLE specialization classes. In addition, the mentioned research concludes that currently among the TLE specializations offered by Rizal High School, a mismatch of taken TLE specialization and student preferences occurs.

Objectives of the Proposed Intervention Program

The proposed intervention program of Rizal High School aims to perform the following specific objectives:

To enlighten the target student population with their strengths, skills, and personality types based on the Realistic, Investigative, Artistic, Social, Enterprising, and Conventional (RIASEC) model.

To align the personality traits of the students and their TLE specialization once these learners are enrolled in grade nine junior high school.

To prepare the school administration in allocating the resources, number of teachers, and slot vacancies for the specific TLE specialization.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

John Holland's Career Choice Theory guided the researcher to draft a contextualized assessment tool catering to the interests, skills and hobbies of the grade nine student-respondents. It was concluded that the dominant personality of students is connected to their skills, interests, and hobbies which modifications were made in Holland's RIASEC assessment tool, aligning the statements categorization to the Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) specializations offered at Rizal High School.

The researcher developed a contextualized assessment tool with verbal interpretations strongly agreed by the experts that concludes for the statements that the items of the instrument show a balance of content with the objectives it is directed at and the instrument reflects well-written instructions for the respondents. It can be concluded that the contextualized questionnaire covered enough items that gives accuracy to the assessment of students.

The grade nine student respondents are more social in trait and are service-minded people. They take bliss in facilitating the growth, learning, and participation of others in group activities. The RIASEC trait result of the assessment tool is significant to the TLE specialization result of the student respondents.

Cookery as a TLE specialization provides an outlet for creativity aligned with being social individuals. Students have the opportunity to showcase their individuality through cookery TLE specialization, experimenting with various flavors, and presenting their dishes in visually captivating manners.

The actual TLE specialization of the grade nine students, when they took the contextualized assessment, does not match their interests based on the result of the mentioned assessment tool.

The study reveals that there is a notable contrast between the overall TLE specialization of student respondents in their ninth-grade year and the outcomes of the contextualized questionnaire they underwent. The questionnaire, which reflects their interests, suggests that the preferred TLE specialization of the participants does not match their actual TLE focus. It can be concluded that students preferred to take the TLE Specialization where their interests lie and thrive in that specific TLE specialization.

The actual study reveals that the age and family income of the student-respondents do not affect their preferred TLE specialization, or the result of the contextualized assessment tool administered to them. It is implied that students are motivated more by their passions and goals rather than external influences like age and family income. In addition, this study reveals the importance of providing opportunities for students to explore and pursue their interests regardless of their background.

This study concludes that the sex of the respondents where females are notable participants, had an effect on their choice of TLE specialization after the administration of the mentioned questionnaire. Women have been associated with domestic roles and responsibilities, including cooking and meal preparation that can be learned in a cookery TLE specialization. As a result, many female respondents of the actual study feel a natural inclination towards taking cookery as a TLE specialization.

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